

The Extent of the Impact of Job Rotation Requirements on Developing Insurance Performance (An applied research in the National Insurance Company)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p data-bbox="193 499 368 528">Article History</p> <p data-bbox="193 562 352 622">Received: May 10, 2021</p> <p data-bbox="193 656 384 716">Accepted: August 24, 2021</p> <hr/> <p data-bbox="193 750 459 837">Keywords : Job Rotation, Insurance Performance</p> <p data-bbox="193 871 480 931">DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5250125</p>	<p data-bbox="555 499 1393 1072"><i>The research aims to shed light on the extent of the impact of job recycling requirements in developing insurance performance in the National Insurance Company, as companies have become more interested in the human resource as the primary resource for them, and seek to develop and develop their capabilities and skills in order to develop performance and achieve the goal that was established for it, as Several modern methods and methods have been used to achieve this, and one of the most important of these methods is the method of job recycling as one of the methods of career development and organizational change that is used to evaluate the performance of employees and direct them towards creativity and innovation to cope with the changes in their environment, and the recycling of A job means that the employee is directed to do other business in an organized and scheduled manner according to a well-studied management plan, To achieve this, the research relied on the analysis of its variables on the questionnaire as a main tool for collecting data and information. The applied results showed that there is a positive and moral effect of the requirements of job recycling in the insurance performance, and this is a good indication of the effect of job recycling requirements in developing the insurance performance of the company the research sample.</i></p>

Introduction

Job rotation is the basis for movement and movement in public and private companies, and it is one of the most important strategies for developing the performance of employees and companies alike. This is done by providing employees with new

experiences and various skills, and at the same time working to pump new blood into the company, and therefore has a major role in developing performance, focusing on the basic and strategic competencies of employees, therefore, it was necessary for the National Insurance Company to take care to attract human qualifications and qualify them through guidance and training to acquire the necessary expertise and skills, and it is also necessary to work on developing them and developing them in line with their requirements to face the changes surrounding them, due to the important and vital role that these companies plays in society, with the services they provide, contribute to the stability, protection and security of society.

The process of developing the insurance performance must obtain leadership support in addition to the specialized departments of the National Insurance Company fulfilling their duty towards this development using the latest strategies that are appropriate to the circumstances surrounding them, with the aim of achieving the greatest benefit from its human resources.

The research problem was crossed by several questions, including what are the requirements for job recycling and the readiness of the National Insurance Company to implement them?. What is the effect of the dimensions of job rotation requirements (training, experience and skill, systems and procedures, strategic development) on the insurance performance of the research sample company?, Hence the importance of research in this topic has emerged through the study of new variables for the dimension of job recycling requirements, which is represented in (training, experience and skill, systems and procedures, strategic development) which can be used in developing the insurance performance to study and analyze the nature of the relationship between the dimensions of job recycling requirements and the extent of their impact on the insurance performance of the National Insurance Company. (Badr, Nidal Salam, 2016) study refers to job recycling and its role in productive efficiency in Palestinian ministries in the Gaza Strip.

Four requirements have been studied from job rotation (training, job design, career development strategy, systems and procedures), it also aimed at identifying the productive efficiency of employees at the higher administrative levels, the first category and the head of a division of the second category.

The study population is of the highest and first category and the head of a section of the second category of (1863) employees. The study data was collected through the use of a questionnaire consisting of (65)

paragraphs, distributed to (380) employees using the random sample method, and it were possible to collect (307) questionnaire valid for analysis. The response rate to the total distributed questionnaires reached (80.7%). The study concluded on several points, the most important of which was the career development strategy in the first place among the requirements for job recycling in its impact on the level of productive efficiency in the ministries, followed by the design of the jobs followed, then followed by training and capacity development and the systems and procedures in the ministries came in the last.

There is a positive relationship between the requirements of job recycling with its four dimensions and productive efficiency, and that there are statistically significant differences between the averages of the study sample estimates about the field of systems and procedures due to the number of years of experience in favor of those whose years of experience range from (4 to less than 8 years). As for the study (Abbasi, Sarsvani, 2013) "The effect of job recycling on performance by taking diversity skills and job satisfaction for bank employees Iran" the study aimed to highlight the effects of job recycling patterns on employee performance, by taking into account the diversity of skills and job satisfaction in mind and providing principles An effective directive to enable managers to lead the company towards a better future according to the required policies, and the SPSS program was used to test the relationship between job recycling and performance, and the study concluded that work performance is not directly affected by job recycling, and that job recycling positively affects job performance through the satisfaction and the differences in the skills.

1- Methodology

1-1- Research Problem

The problem can be formulated with the following questions:

- 1- What are the requirements for job recycling and the readiness of the National Insurance Company to implement them?
- 2- What is the reality of insurance performance in the National Insurance Company?
- 3- What are the factors that help in developing insurance performance?
- 4- What is the effect of the dimensions of the requirements of job recycling (training, experience and skill, systems and procedures, strategic development) on the insurance performance of the company in the research sample?

1-2- Research importance

The research derives its importance from:

- Study new variables for the dimension of the requirements for job recycling, which is represented in (training, experience and skill, systems and procedures, strategic development), which can be used to develop insurance performance.
- Studying and analyzing the nature of the relationship between the dimensions of job recycling requirements and the extent of their impact on the insurance performance of the National Insurance Company.

1-3- Research Objectives

The research seeks to achieve the following goals:

- Shedding light on the reality of the requirements for job recycling in the National Insurance Company, using a number of related measures and indicators.
- Knowing the level of insurance performance in the company, the research sample and its implications for its outputs.
- Knowing the nature of the relationship between the existence of job recycling requirements within this company and insurance performance from the point of view of the research sample.

1.4 Research Hypothesis

The research is based on the following hypotheses:

- 1- There is a statistically significant correlation between the requirements for job recycling and insurance performance.
- 2- There is a statistically significant effect of job recycling requirements on insurance performance.
- 3- There is a statistically significant multiple effects of the dimensions of job recycling requirements combined in insurance performance.

1.5 Field and research data

- 1- **Time limits:** The research was completed during the year 2020.
- 2- **Spatial limits:** The National Insurance Company.

1.6 Methodology of the study

The study relied on the experimental and analytical method by collecting the necessary data and analyzing it. The fact that this approach focuses on seeking opinions about the research sample and its directions, and using the descriptive approach; To describe the reality of the studied variables, and the analytical approach, it is used to analyze the results of statistical treatments for research variables, and to draw conclusions on the basis of adopting recommendations.

1.7 Analysis tools

The questionnaire, which represented the main tool for collecting information on the research, was distributed for the period from (13/1/2020) to (16/2/2020). The questionnaire was divided into two main parts, the first of which was general information about the characteristics of the research sample, and the second consisted of (30) paragraphs. It was divided into two axes: the first axis consists of (20) items related to measuring the requirements for job recycling, and the second axis is composed of (10) paragraphs related to measuring the insurance performance.

1.8 Research problems and difficulties:

- 1- The lack or scarcity of references, studies and scientific research on the topic of job rotation, as it is considered one of the new topics in the field of research and studies.
- 2- Difficulty in obtaining information from the National Insurance Company.

1.9 Research Form

Based on the opinions of a number of researchers in previous studies that review the independent variable (requirements for job recycling), which is defined in four dimensions (training, experience and skill, systems and procedures, strategic development), and its impact on the dependent variable (insurance performance), as shown in the figure 1.

Figure 1: research hypothesis diagram

1.10 Research community and sample

In order to test the hypotheses of the study and achieve its goals, the researcher has chosen the sample (probability class) from the study community in the National Insurance Company, which is represented by the following certificates (PhD, MA, Higher Diploma, Bachelor, and Diploma), considering that these certificates are closer to the subject of the study, and the size of the community according to the statistics of the commission reached (200) individuals, and the sample size of this community was determined according to the global model (De Morgan, D. Morgan) to determine the sample size at the level of significance (0.05) until (0.01), since the sample size according to this model was (127) individuals, i.e. (64%) of the total study population, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Determining sample size from a given population

N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S
10	10	100	80	280	162	800	260	2800	338
15	14	110	86	290	165	850	265	3000	341
20	19	120	92	300	169	900	269	3500	246
25	24	130	97	320	175	950	274	4000	351
30	28	140	103	340	181	1000	278	4500	351
35	32	150	108	360	186	1100	285	5000	357
40	36	160	113	380	181	1200	291	6000	361
45	40	180	118	400	196	1300	297	7000	364
50	44	190	123	420	201	1400	302	8000	367
55	48	200	127	440	205	1500	306	9000	368
60	52	210	132	460	210	1600	310	10000	370

65	56	220	136	480	214	1700	313	15000	375
70	59	230	140	500	217	1800	317	20000	377
75	63	240	144	550	225	1900	320	30000	379
80	66	250	148	600	234	2000	322	40000	380
85	70	260	152	650	242	2200	327	50000	381
90	73	270	155	700	248	2400	331	75000	382
95	76	270	159	750	256	2600	335	100000	384

" N " is population size Note

" s " is sample size

(127) questionnaires were distributed to the sample. On the other hand, the number of forms received and fulfilling the requirements of analysis and study from the sample, which were answered, reached (125) questionnaires. Table 2 shows the study sample, the number of distributed, received forms, and the percentage of their retrieval.

Table 2: Sample distribution

Sample community	No. of distributed forms	No. of received forms	Rate of return%
National Insurance Company	127	125	98.4%

1.11 Measuring honesty and consistency:

1- Honesty test: The researcher presented the questionnaire form to a group of arbitrators with expertise in the field of research. The researcher responded to the arbitrators' opinions and made the necessary changes in light of the submitted proposals, and the questionnaire was finalized.

2- Stability test: Stability means that the questionnaire gives the same result if it was redistributed more than once under the same conditions and conditions, and that the test of stability here is according to the CronbachAlfe equation in the case of a test in which the scores are estimated (not one or zero), but it can take different values (1, 2, 3, 4,...), as in the case of tests that use a Likert scale, as mentioned above to answer paragraphs. This equation is also used in tests of the type of substantive or essay questions (Al-Jadri and Abu Hilo, 2009: 171). Table 3 shows the stability test for the study variables.

Table 3: Stability test of the research variables using Cronbach's Coefficient

No.	Variables	Cronbach's Coefficient
1-	Job rotation requirements X	0.983
2-	Insurance performance Y	0.977
3-	Total research variables	0.978

It is clear from the above table that the value of the Cronbach Coefficient alpha is high for each of the research variables, and the total value of the research variables of the alpha coefficient has reached (0.978), which is a high stability value, and this result confirms the validity and consistency of the study questionnaire and its validity for application to the basic study sample.

1.12 Statistical tools and methods used in data processing and analysis

The researcher relied on a number of tools for statistical analysis and processing, as follows:

- 1- Ready statistical package (Spss - Ver - 19): used to extract the results.
- 2- Microsoft Excel 2010 used for data analysis.

2 Theoretical review

2.1 The concept of job rotation

Job rotation is one of the latest methods that have been reached through modern management in its application to employees by giving them the opportunity to practice more than one organized work, whether recycling within the company or to another company, and job recycling is defined as "the process of transferring the employee from one job to another in order to earn it skills and expertise that do not give him the ability to face multiple work problems with high efficiency without resorting to management." (Bozidi, 2017: 11).

(Al-Sharif, 2011: 714) sees job rotation as "an effective tool and a dynamic pillar towards developing work, as it is defined as the transfer of a manager or leader from work to work according to specific goals and in accordance with specific regulations." And it was also identified as "exposing the new employee to multiple job experiences by transferring him temporarily from one job to another and helps to get to know other employees, their activities and the work environment in which they work." (Qorari, Ayachi, 2019: 7)

As for (Abu Sabha, 2014: 9), job rotation was defined as "a planned movement of individuals from one job to another in order to develop their skills and their understanding of work, meaning that this process is considered a planned process and is a type of on-the-job training"

The importance of job rotation was highlighted through: (Jones & Georth, 2003: 555)

1. Job rotation is used to employ a group of individuals in order to prepare them and prepare them for job training.
2. The ability of job recycling to solve problems that occurred in human resources management and find a solution to them gradually and correctly, as what has been applied job recycling in companies in the best image.
3. It contributes to increasing the diversity of the skill of the working individual through rotating it for several jobs, or job locations in the company's departments.
4. It represents an active contribution in preparing the human angel by creating a kind of congruence between the capabilities of the individual, his duties and responsibilities, as it requires dependence on an efficient administration and full knowledge of what the departments and departments contain in terms of skills and actions to determine how necessary to make the movements within the single administration and between the possible departments.

2.2 Dimensions of job rotation requirements:

Job rotation is one of the modern methods used in companies that seek to flourish and advance their companies and improve their performance and achieve their various goals. It is also one of the most important strategies for the development of employee performance and this is achieved by using the dimensions of job rotation requirements, which we highlight, some of them in this study, and the current research deals with these dimensions with the following detailed:

1. Training

Good training leads to the transformation of the human cadre within any administrative company into a fruitful individual of the company capable of achieving goals and providing services and improving performance during specific training time periods, There is a big difference between companies that are interested in the matter of training for the development of their members and those that leave matters to fate. One of the strategies that training in the company performs for employees in various sectors is to prepare these individuals and leave a clear impact on the performance of their tasks and develop their expertise in job tasks to be performed at the work level and to ensure the company's reputation and provide the best (Badr, 2016: 24).

The training has been defined as "a planned, organized, and continuous process aimed at developing the skills and capabilities of the individual, increasing his information, and improving his behavior and directions so that he can efficiently and effectively function" (Tahir, Muhammad, 2018: 54), the training objectives are to contribute to the development of human capabilities in companies to help individuals and companies achieve the desired goals and increase the high performance of the individuals working for them. Also, the training process is an effective way to increase the efficiency of individuals within any company. Training often leads to increasing the acquisition of new skills and experiences and stimulating the spirit of competition between individuals and employees to receive more new information and develop their performance at work and gain a new type of new skill within the work, which is a type of development that the official within the company must implement in practice on the ground. The objectives of training were focused on some points that the company can benefit from within the administration and are as follows: (Al-Madani, 2009: 33)

- 1- Raising the level in terms of performance of individuals working in the company and improving their level of performance, which is considered as one of the main goals of any company?
- 2- Maintain the devices and tools that exist inside the company.
- 3- Training contributes greatly to the implementation of the company strategy.

2- Experience and skill

The strength of experience emerges from the important information and knowledge of intellectual assets, or the skills that are acquired in the context of organizational interaction (Daft, 2016: 223), on this basis, companies focused on developing and developing their intellectual capital, in order to raise the level of their skill and expertise to the level that led to influencing the superior performance of these companies through the process of rotation and recycling of human resources that possess knowledge in those companies, the educated company and administrative information systems that in Its basis aimed to counter strong competition to achieve its strategic success (Arora, 2002: 240), and that successful companies should think about their human resources and provide the best services to their customers, and make special efforts to make them happy, more efficient and perform their roles by raising their skills and knowledge and empowering them in order to give activated doses to add organizational value to their business (Alwan and others, 2018 265)

3- Systems and procedures

Companies that work robustly and thoughtfully in establishing their strategic procedures, and developing and improving the skills of their employees have more learning abilities that support change and innovation.

Managers are highly interested in managing employees and urging them to innovate in the services provided by the company. To understand employee productivity, two systems can be addressed by the human resources management in the company, the first is the traditional system and the second is the innovative system and they are used so far in the first place (Selden & MacMillan, 2006 : 108), (Osterman, 2006: 187).

- **Traditional system:** This system depends on the style of individual incentives, as it depends on the design of individual jobs, and does not depend on the method of job recycling, as the individual incentives method indicates that rewards for employees are based on their individual performance. As for the individual-based work design, it refers to the tasks that were specifically designed for employees to be performed individually. This system has been used since 1960 in the United States and therefore it is called the traditional system. (Ichniowski& Shaw, 2003: 55).
- **Innovative system:** This system relies on the practice of human resources, problem solving teams, incentive payment plans, careful selection and employment, and has effective communication systems between employees and management, there are some practices that intersect with each other, such as designing jobs that depend on the team model, and the incentive model based on the team, as well as job rotation in designing jobs based on the team. There are a set of overlapping functions and tasks that team members perform to perform tasks that require the involvement of employees from different jobs and multiple divisions. The team-based incentive system is the incentives or compensation that the team receives as a result of performing a set of overlapping tasks, and it means that individuals are awarded the reward on the basis of the team performance in various jobs and not based on their personal performance. (Gant & Shaw, 2002: 289).

4- Strategic development:

Contemporary companies contribute to helping employees determine their professional inclinations and identify strengths and weaknesses in their skill and perceptions of their professional goals through what is called the process of strategic development. It is the process by which employees are more aware and aware of their professional inclinations, their values, strengths and weaknesses through the information provided by the company about opportunities and making information available to employees about the nature of jobs and locations in the company and helping to define their professional goals and appropriate methods to achieve the desired goals, hence, the definition of strategic development is that it is "the process of designing and implementing goals and strategies in order to satisfy employees' desires and achieve their aspirations for progress".

The company looking to succeed is the one that provides the opportunity for employees to show their skills to serve the company and achieve their personal ambitions together. The success of the company is not guaranteed by product quality, capital intensity, or multiplicity of markets, but rather the human element, talents, ambitions, and potentials that drive the company to keep pace with change and innovation (Al-Kurdi and Al-Attar, 2011).

The strategic development leads to some positives, including: (Maher, 2008: 325)

- ❖ **Achieving the goals of both individuals and the company:** If the employees aim to develop and grow in the work, then the companies seek to achieve productivity, profit and career planning in what it achieves from the position of the right man and thus achieve the two goals together.
- ❖ **Improving the company's reputation:** If employees realize that their company takes care of their future career, they actively help to promote the company in all societies and places where they may be, which ultimately leads to improving the company's image.
- ❖ **The strategic development** focuses on achieving compatibility between employees on one hand and between jobs and career growth on the other hand, that is, at the individual level or at the company level.

2.3 The concept of insurance performance

"It is a vivid image that reflects the result of the company's level in exploiting its resources and its ability to achieve the goals set by the various activities and applying the standards that suit the company and the nature of its work" (Hamad, 2013: 1042-1043). Insurance performance is defined as "all the consequences of the activities and practices undertaken by the company that are expected to meet the planned and set goals" (David, 2001). It was defined as "a reflection of the company's ability and ability to achieve its long-term goals, and in accordance with the established criteria in light of its interaction with internal and external changes, It is an idea that reflects the company's ability to grow, survive and adapt by responding to environmental changes, and performance has been said in the simplest form of results that the company seeks to achieve "(Al-Dawi, 2017: 10). Another definition of insurance performance was defined as "a practical tool for managers to discover how to reach good decisions and the performance of their employees" (Hatefi&Boroumand, 2009: 1).

Insurance performance is a prominent importance in various national insurance companies, as these companies try to achieve the best performance of insurance services to ensure their survival and continuity in the business

environment, it is the end result of the company's activities in the exploitation of its resources to achieve the goals set according to criteria compatible with the nature of the company's work.

There are several reasons that called for attention to the level of developing the insurance performance of national insurance companies, including: (Harry, 2010: 16)

- 1- The changing of the nature of the work as a result of the economic, political, social and environmental conditions that impose themselves on the nature of insurance services provided to the final customer.
- 2- Increased competition in insurance markets as a result of what insurance companies offer from services that meet the purposes and needs of the customer.
- 3- Innovations and continuous improvement, as insurance companies periodically improve insurance services as a result of technological innovations that help in providing services better, with less time and cost to the customer.
- 4- Change in organizational performance as a result of different insurance purposes, differing needs and desires of the customer, and increased competition in the markets pushing insurance companies to provide the best services quickly and as a result of their use in information technology, which affects changing the organizational structure of national insurance companies.
- 5- Change in external requests, insurance companies are constantly changing due to the difference in customer preferences, as insurance companies are required to be always ready to provide various insurance services as a result of the change in external requests.
- 6- The power of information technology, which is expressed by the power of the insurance company in its possession of information technology that benefits from it in the process of planning, managing and satisfying the desires of the customer through human resources with experience qualified to manage and operate the technological force used in the insurance company.

Empirical Analysis and Test

Empirical Analysis

This aspect seeks to clarify the most important characteristics of the members of the research sample from workers in the National Insurance Company, through the information included in the questionnaire that was distributed to them, and here comes a brief description of the members of the research sample.

- **Gender:** Table 4 shows that the number of males reached (64) individuals, or (51.2%) of the total study sample of (125). As for the percentage of females, the number of its members reached (61), i.e. (48.8%) of the total study sample.

- **Age:** Table 4 shows that the age group (30 years or less) has a number of its members (76), i.e. (60.8%) of the total study sample, which is (125), which is the highest percentage, followed by the age group between (31-40 years), it constituted (31) individuals, i.e. (24.8%), followed by the age group between (41 - 50 years), when it achieved (11) individuals, i.e. (8.8%), and finally the group (more than 50 years) formed (7) individuals which equals to, which explains to us that the organization owns a variety of staff, not specific to a stage, or a specific age group, and this gives strength to study in terms of taking the views of most of the age groups in the organization. (5.6%)

- **Scientific level:** Table 4 shows that the vast majority of the sample members have a bachelor's degree, since they numbered 91 people out of the total study sample, which is (125), or (72.8%), which is the highest percentage, while the number of those holding a diploma reached (20) individuals, i.e. (16.0%), followed by the number of those holding a master's degree, as the number of its members reached (8) individuals, which is (6.4%), followed by the number of those holding a doctorate, and the post graduated diploma, where they numbered (3) individuals each, or (2.4%) of the total study sample. This indicates that the majorities of the sample members have a good culture, and have sufficient scientific ability to answer the questions of the questionnaire, which makes the answers more accurate and objective.

- **Years of Service:** Table 4 shows that the service period (less than 5 years) achieved the highest percentage, the number of its members reached (85) individuals, i.e. (68.0%) of the total study sample of (125), while the service period achieved from (5-10 years) (21) individuals, i.e. (16.8%), and finally, the service period achieved (11 years - more) (19) individuals, i.e. (15.2) of the total sample, it is evident that the researched sample is characterized by intellectual maturity and skillful integration between all levels, and this creates strength for study, especially in the sample's response to the questionnaire paragraphs, in terms of understanding and comprehension.

Table 4: Characteristics of Sample Members

No.	Variables	Categories	Repetition	Percent %
1	Gender	Male	64	51.2
		Female	61	48.8
		Total	125	100.0
		30 years and less	76	60.8
		31-40 years	31	24.8

2	Age	41-50 years	11	8.8
		51 years and over	7	5.6
		Total	125	100.0
3	Educational Degree	Doctorate	3	2.4
		Master	8	6.4
		Post Graduate Diploma	3	2.4
		Bachelor	91	72.8
		Diploma	20	16.0
		Total	125	100.0
4	Years of Experience	Less than 5 years	85	68.0
		From 5 to 10 years	21	16.8
		More than 11 years	19	15.2
		Total	125	100.0

3.2 Study hypotheses test

In this topic, the study hypotheses that were laid down in the methodology of the study, which relates to the study variables, represented in the requirements of job rotation as an independent variable, and the dependent variable represented by insurance performance, will be examined.

1- The correlation hypothesis test: This topic seeks to determine the nature of the relationship between the variables of the study, to find out the extent to which the first main hypothesis is accepted or rejected: There is a statistically significant correlation relationship with functional rotation requirements with insurance performance, using the simple correlation coefficient (Pearson Correlation Coefficient), which is one of the statistical methods used to measure the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables at the level of the study sample.

It is clear from Table No. (5) and Figure (2) that there is a positive correlation with positive (significant) moral significance between the requirements of job rotation and insurance performance, and the correlation relationship has reached its value (0.797 **) at a significance level (0.01).

The number of moral relationships (5) was 100%, and the highest sub-value of correlation coefficients in this axis was between training application and insurance performance, as its value reached (0.833 **), at the level of significance (0.01).

This expresses the existence of a relationship of moral significance and its function and explains the strength of the relationship between training and insurance performance. Hence, we infer the acceptance of the first major hypothesis, according to which there is a statistically significant correlation with positive moral requirements for job rotation in insurance performance as shown in Figure 2 and Table 5.

Table 5: The correlation between the requirements for job recycling and insurance performance

Job rotation requirements X		Moral relations					Insurance performance Y	
							Training	Experience and skill
Organizational performance Y	Coefficient of correlation	0.833**	0.722**	0.761**	0.732**	0.797**	5	100%
	Moral level	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
	The decision	Function	Function	Function	Function	Function		

** Strength of Relationship and Morality (1%)

* The strength of the moral relationship (5%)

Figure 2: The correlation between the requirements for job rotation and insurance performance

2- Impact hypothesis testing

The current study has developed the second and third major hypothesis, which is the Simple Regression Analysis hypothesis, and the Multi Regression Analysis hypothesis.

1- Simple Regression Analysis Hypothesis

It is clear from Table 6 that the calculated value of (F) has reached (103.936), which is greater than the (F) table value of (6.87) at the level of significance (1%), and with significance (0.000) and with a degree of freedom (1.123), and this result means that there is a statistically significant and significant effect of the respondent variable (job rotation requirements) in the dependent variable (insurance performance) in the research sample. As for the value of the determination factor (R²), its value reached (0.456), and this result indicates that (the requirements for job recycling) explain what is (45.6%) of the difference in (insurance performance), and that (54.4%) is an explanation of the varied factors that did not enter the regression model. Accordingly, these results provide sufficient support for the acceptance of the second main research hypothesis, which states **(There is significant effect of job rotation requirements on insurance performance)**.

Through table 6, we note that the value of the fixed term (a = 0.602) is statistically significant, as the calculated value of t was (1.691) and it is greater than the tabular t at the level of significance 5% and the degree of freedom (123) and (1.67), the value of the marginal slope (b = 0.877) is statistically significant because the calculated t value of 10.194 is greater than the tabular t at the level of significance% 1 and the degree of freedom (123) and it is (2.34), and these results confirm that there is a strong influence of the requirements of career rotation in the insurance performance in the National Insurance Company.

Table 6: Explains the effect of job rotation requirements on insurance performance

Independent variable \ Dependent variable	Tax success							
	Fixed Limit a	Calculated Value of T	Marginal inclination B	Calculated Value of T	Selection coefficient R ²	Calculated Value of F	Mortality	Decision
Job rotation requirements	0.602	1.691	0.877	10.194	0.456	103.936	0.000	There is an effect

*The value (f) of the table at a significant level 0.05 and the degrees of freedom (1.23) = (3.91),

** The value (f) of the table at a significant level 0.01 and the degrees of freedom (1,123) = (6.87)

* Value (t) tabular at a significant level 0.05 and degrees of freedom (123) = (1.67)

** Value (t) tabular at a significant level 0.01 and two degrees freedom (123) = (2.34)

2. Multi Regression Analysis Hypothesis

It was laid down in the methodology of the third major hypothesis study, according to which the dimensions of job rotation requirements are affected (Training, experience and skill, systems and procedures, strategic development) in a positive and moral sense in the insurance performance of the National Insurance Company. It is clear from Table 7, that the calculated value of (F) has reached (117.187), which is greater than the (F) table

value of (3.19) at the level of significance (0.01), with significance (0.000), and with a degree of freedom (5,119), this result means that there is a statistically significant effect of the respondent variable (sum of the variables (X) of job rotation requirements) in the dependent variable (insurance performance), in the research sample. As for the value of the determining factor (R²), it was (0.897), which means that (the sum of the variables (X) of the requirements for functional recycling) explain what percentage (89.7%) of the variance that occurs in (insurance performance), and that (10.3%) is an explanatory variation of factors that did not enter the regression model.

Accordingly, these results provide sufficient support to accept the hypothesis of multiple effect, the third main research which states **(there is a significant effect of the sum of the variables (X) combined, the requirements for job rotation in the insurance performance)**.

Through table 7, we note that the value of the constant term ($a = 0.133$) is statistically significant, as the calculated value of t is (1.178), it is less than the tabular t at the level of significance 5% and the degree of freedom (119) and adult (1.67), while the value of the marginal inclination (experience and skill), it has reached ($b = 0.146$) and is statistically insignificant because its calculated value of (0.852) is less than the tabular t of (1.67) at the significance level (0.05) and with a degree of freedom (119). As for the value of the current slope (training, systems and procedures, strategic development), it reached ($b = 0.625, 0.457, 0.694$) respectively, it is statistically significant because its calculated value of t (3.165, 5.732 and 9.977) respectively, it is greater than the tabular t of (2.34) at the significance level (0.01) and with a degree of freedom (119).

In light of these results, it is clear that the requirements for job recycling with their combined variables have a strong moral effect on the insurance performance in the National Insurance Company.

Table 7: Multiple effect sum of variables (X) requirements for job rotation in insurance performance

Job rotation requirements	Insurance performance						
	Regression coefficients	Calculated t	Morality	Determination Coefficient R ²	Calculated F	Morality	Decision
Fixed Limit	0.133	1.178	0.320	0.897	117.187	0.000	There is Effect
Training	0.625	3.165	0.003				
Experience and Skill	0.146	0.852	0.396				
Systems and Procedures	0.457	5.732	0.000				
Strategic Development	0.694	9.977	0.000				

* The value (f) of the table at a significant level 0.05 and the degrees of freedom (5,119) = (2.30)

** The value (f) of the table at a significant level 0.01 and the degrees of freedom (5,119) = (3.19)

* Value (t) tabular at a significant level 0.05 and degrees of freedom (119) = (1.67)

** Value (t) tabular at the level of 0.01 and degrees of freedom (119) = (2.34).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusions

- 1- There is a positive and moral correlation between the requirements for job rotating and insurance performance.
- 2- There is a positive and moral effect of the requirements of job rotating in the insurance performance.
- 3- There is a positive multi-effect of the sum of the variables of job rotating requirements combined in the insurance performance.
- 4- Weak technological means in the company that helps workers gain experience.
- 5- There is little use of technologies and the Internet to obtain advanced knowledge.
- 6- Weakness in work teams and periodic meetings regarding job rotating.

4.2 Recommendations

In light of the results reached, the following recommendations can be taken:

- 1- Development of technological means in the company that help workers diagnose and gain experience.
- 2- Urging the use of technologies and the Internet to obtain advanced knowledge.
- 3- Increase work teams and hold periodic meetings related to job rotating.
- 4- Holding training courses for the employees of the company continuously by experienced experts internally and externally on the application of job rotating.

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